

DYNAMICS OF STRATEGIC EDUCATIONAL PLANNING IN PROMOTING LEADERSHIP INTEGRITY IN NIGERIAN COLLEGES OF EDUCATION

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Abstract

*Giving the importance of strategic educational planning and its impact on various administrative variables, such as leadership integrity, this study paper explored the dynamics of strategic educational planning in promoting leadership integrity in Nigerian Colleges of Education. A cross-sectional survey of 208 participants, selected through purposive sampling technique, using a valid and reliable structured questionnaire that incorporated all research variables was used for data collection. A questionnaire containing the research scales were administered and data collected. Data collected was analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation with 0.05 level of significance given the choice of the confidence interval of 95%. Findings revealed that there existed a statistically significant positive correlation between leadership behavioural integrity and strategic educational planning, with a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.407^{**}$ and a p -value < 0.01 . Result revealed a statistically significant positive correlation between leadership moral behaviour and strategic educational planning, with a correlation coefficient of $r = .342^{**}$ and a p -value < 0.01 . Result revealed a statistically significant positive correlation between leadership consistency and strategic educational planning, with a correlation coefficient of $r = .435^{**}$ and a p -value < 0.01 . The researcher therefore recommended that institutional leaders should lead by example, thereby demonstrating the virtues of integrity, as it played a major role in enhancing successful strategic educational planning in a meaningful way.*

Keywords: Strategic educational planning, Leadership integrity, Nigerian Colleges of Education

Introduction

Leadership integrity is a cornerstone of effective governance and ethical practice in educational institutions. In Nigeria, as in many other countries, the quality of leadership significantly influences the success and reputation of academic institutions. Integrity in leadership encompasses honesty, transparency, accountability, and consistency in actions and decision-making. It is essential for building trust among staff, students, parents, and the wider community. Enwereuzo (2023) indicated that leadership qualities and human resource management in universities stand as the nucleus of the success of any Institution.

According to Adeshipo and Harrison (2018) leader's behaviour is crucial for promoting organizational effectiveness, and integrity has been more specifically defined as a principled value characterized by openness, consistency, and fairness, it can also be viewed as a value for an individual or an organization. Leadership integrity is the persistent commitment of leaders to moral and ethical standards in their relationships, decisions, and behaviour. As a result, when faced with morally challenging decisions, leaders with integrity show honesty, openness, and dedication to doing the right thing (Yukl, 2012).

Moorman, Darnold and Priesemuth (2013) conceptualised leadership integrity into three category behavioral integrity, moral behavior and consistency. Leadership behavioral integrity can be defined as the perceived pattern of alignment between the leader's words and deeds or, in other words, the extent that leaders are seen as practicing what they preach. From time to time, supervisors adopt a certain set of norms and values, but sometimes their actions lack these newly embedded sets of values, which reflect a breach of trust of the followers (Ishaq et al., 2021). This misalignment of words and actions is generally the result of a target achievement craze or requirement, which negatively impacts their subordinates and the work environment.

Monga (2016) referencing Mayer et al. (1995) proposed that integrity is rooted in moral values as perceived by followers, defining it as the follower's belief that a leader adheres to a set of principles aligned with their own. A leader's past actions, communication from others about the leader, their perceived sense of justice, and alignment with group values all influence the degree to which the leader is seen as having integrity. This suggests a broader view of integrity, encompassing both consistency and moral values.

Monga (2016) added that integrity also involves maintaining consistency in the face of adversity. Leadership consistency refers to the alignment between a leader's actions, decisions, and expressed values over time, fostering trust and credibility among followers. Consistent leaders demonstrate reliability by maintaining a steady adherence to their principles, ensuring their behaviour matches their stated goals and commitments. This steadiness not only builds trust but also enhances organizational stability and follower confidence, particularly during periods of uncertainty.

In addition, leadership is a means to motivate staff for greater performance and productivity, thereby helping them to gain increased job satisfaction. The effective control of any system is facilitated by an effective leader/leader with integrity and this is considered to be basic in achieving effectiveness in any institution (Ololube, 2024). However, Leadership plays a central role in institutions and in the world at large. Hence the leader must strive to fundamentally and appropriately build a balance with regards to the different behaviors of subordinates for varying situation to be effective.

Furthermore, Bass (2015) emphasized the pivotal role of leadership styles in shaping the strategic planning process. Leadership, defined by its components of inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, individualized consideration, and idealized influence, is particularly effective in fostering a shared vision and inspiring commitment among stakeholders. However, given the volatile environment in which higher education institutions operate, particularly in Nigeria, there is an urgent need for strategic planning. Such planning is essential for determining the optimal direction for institutions, as its absence can lead to serious consequences that negatively affect future outcomes (Alyosfi, 2020). To achieve performance excellence and enhance competitiveness, institutions must adopt strategic planning that is flexible, adaptive, and focused on their vision, mission, goals, policies, and procedures (Karam & Kitana, 2020).

Aydın, Karakulle and Polat (2022) view planning as the source of strategic thinking that governs the long-term activities of organizations according to a specific discipline. In other words, it serves as an essential tool for coordinating activities, dividing labor, ensuring sectoral specialization, managing finances effectively, and optimizing the use of human resources. Consequently, Aydın et al. (2022) argue that strategic planning contributes significantly to organizational performance. Wittmann and Reuter (2008) observe that a successful strategy requires understanding surrounding circumstances, the power of rivals, and a suitable approach to engage relevant parties.

Strategy is a tactical process that enables organizations to leverage core competencies and gain a competitive advantage. Organizations determine the best course of action by evaluating the state of their competitors while formulating their strategy (Hitt, Ireland, & Hoskisson, 2017). Strategy serves as a crucial tool that helps organizations navigate the present and achieve future goals.

Donagh and Branka (2019) asserted that strategic planning is the primary guiding force for business organizations to achieve exceptional performance, ensuring their survival and continuity. It represented a modern approach to change, shifting from arbitrary practices to participatory, innovative, and excellence-driven management.

Strategic planning also addressed future challenges related to management systems, ensuring optimal utilization of material and human resources (Alfurjani & Almntaser, 2019). Its importance lies in its ability to help organizations identify and adapt to changes and trends in their work environment (Krzysztof & Raoul, 2019), mitigate the effects of these changes, and implement plans to address them (Bontempo et al., 2015). David (2009) viewed strategic planning as a fundamental aspect of strategic management, encompassing the process of defining and formulating an organization's mission in line with its core vision, as well as setting its future goals and objectives.

Strategic planning is also regarded as a set of actions, concepts, and tools aimed at achieving diverse organizational benefits, gathering data about internal and external environments, and enhancing decision-making processes (Wolf & Floyd, 2017). Moreover, it played several vital roles with positive impacts on organizations (Cunha & Magalhaes, 2019). Ikedíugwu and Chukwumah (2015), citing Chang (2008), described a strategic plan as a dynamic document that encompasses policy directions, implementation strategies, action plans, execution benchmarks, monitoring and evaluation mechanisms, and an expenditure framework. This framework allowed for adjustments in areas that require development during the implementation phase. A strategic plan involves analyzing a school's developmental issues, prioritizing and planning to address them, and implementing strategies to resolve these challenges. Ultimately, it ensures that learners receive quality education, fostering both total development and academic achievement.

Furthermore, the strategic planning process evaluated strengths and weaknesses while analyzing opportunities and threats within changing environmental conditions. For academic institutions, the most basic way to ensure long-term survival is by cultivating a skilled and competent human resources capacity, along with establishing and implementing long-term goals (Kriemadis & Theakou, 2007). In the process of preparing a strategic plan, the mission and vision of the

institution must be clearly defined. When these are determined with the joint participation of employees, the strategic plan can become a foundation for loyalty, motivating employees to make significant efforts in achieving the institution's goals.

The successful execution of strategic plans depends on leadership integrity. Nangoli et al. (2020) found that leadership integrity fosters a mutually beneficial relationship between the organization, employees, and leaders. Similarly, Purba and Prasetyo (2020) showed that leadership and integrity significantly influence organizational commitment and employee performance. This underscores the importance of leadership integrity in implementing strategic educational planning, ensuring organizational stability and improving performance. Without integrity encompassing behavioural integrity, moral behaviour, and consistency institutions may struggle with effective implementation. Ultimately, successful implementation of strategic plans is essential for an institution's success and survival in the competitive academic environment.

There existed a significant research gap regarding the dynamics of strategic planning in promoting leadership integrity. While prior studies have explored the significant relationships between leadership style and strategic planning processes (Al-Mahdi, 2021), leadership integrity and workers' productive behaviour (Oga & Eketu, 2022), and leadership morality and organizational performance (Marshall, 2020), limited research if any could be found has examined the dynamics of strategic educational planning in fostering leadership integrity among the academic staff of Nigerian colleges. To address this gap in knowledge, particularly within academic settings, this study investigated the role of strategic educational planning in promoting leadership integrity among the academic staff of Nigerian colleges.

Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between leadership behavioral integrity and strategic educational planning among academic staffs of Nigerian Colleges.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between leadership moral behaviour and strategic educational planning among academic staffs of Nigerian Colleges.

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between leadership consistency and strategic educational planning among academic staffs of Nigerian Colleges.

Methodology

The study was conducted among academic staff of colleges of education in the North Central and South west regions of Nigeria. The correlational research design was adopted. A total of two hundred and eight (208) participants was sampled and used for this study. A self-report questionnaire was employed, having three sections, including demographic data, strategic educational planning and leadership integrity. The demographic data included: age, sex, marital status, ethnicity, religion, educational qualification, socio-economic status and years of working experience. Strategic educational planning was measured with 20-item scale out of the original 21-items developed by Aydın, Karakulle and Polat (2022) that measured strategic plan perception. The scale was measured on a five-point Likert type from 1-Totally Disagree, 2-Disagree, 3-No Opinion, 4-Agree and 5-Totally Agree. However, Cronbach's alpha of 0.92 was reported for Strategic educational planning. Leadership integrity was measured with 16-item scale to assess perceived integrity of the leader with three sub-categories such as; leadership behavioural integrity, moral behaviour and consistency as used by Moorman et al.'s (2013). The scale was measured on a five-point Likert type from 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree and 5 = strongly agree. However, Cronbach's alpha of .92 was reported for Strategic educational planning. However, Cronbach's alpha of 0.94 was reported for behavioural integrity, 0.94 for moral and 0.93 was reported for consistency, while 0.96 was reported for overall leadership integrity scale. The researcher obtained approval from the relevant authorities before adopting the purposive sampling technique to recruit participants. They were informed of their right to decide whether to participate and assured of confidentiality. Completed questionnaires were collected immediately, and only those properly filled out were used for data analysis.

Results

The three hypotheses stated were tested using SPSS version 25 (IBM Corp, 2015). Pearson product moment correlation analysis was carried out to determine relationship between the components of leadership integrity (behavioural integrity, moral behaviour and consistency) and dynamics of strategic educational planning academic staff of Nigerian Colleges.

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between leadership behavioural integrity and strategic educational planning among academic staffs of Nigerian Colleges. The hypothesis was tested using Pearson product moment correlation and the result is presented on Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of Pearson product moment correlation showing the relationship between leadership behavioural integrity and strategic educational planning

	1	2	\bar{X}	SD
Strategic educational planning	1		1.50	.50
Leadership behavioural integrity	.407**	1	22.13	3.71

**** Significant at 0.01**

The result from table 1, indicated a statistically significant positive correlation between leadership behavioural integrity and strategic educational planning, with a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.407^{**}$ and a p-value < 0.01 . This suggested that as leadership behavioural integrity increased, strategic educational planning tended to improve in a meaningful way. The strength of the relationship, with a moderate effect size, indicated that leadership behavioural integrity played a substantial role in enhancing strategic educational planning within an educational context. The symbol asterisk (***) confirmed that this relationship was highly significant at the 1% level, reinforcing the reliability of this finding. Therefore, null hypothesis was rejected.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between leadership moral behaviour and strategic educational planning among academic staff of Nigerian Colleges. The hypothesis was tested using Pearson product moment correlation and the result is presented on Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of Pearson product moment correlation showing the relationship between leadership moral behaviour and strategic educational planning

	1	2	\bar{X}	SD
Strategic educational planning	1		1.50	.50
Leadership moral behaviour	.342**	1	23.33	3.79

**** Significant at 0.01**

The result from table 2; indicates a statistically significant positive correlation between leadership moral behaviour and strategic educational planning, with a correlation coefficient of $r = .342^{**}$ and a p-value < 0.01 . This suggested that as leadership moral behaviour increased, strategic educational

planning tended to improve in a meaningful way. The strength of the relationship, with a moderate effect size, indicated that leadership moral behaviour played a substantial role in enhancing strategic educational planning within an educational context. The symbol asterisk (**) confirmed that this relationship was highly significant at the 1% level, reinforcing the reliability of this finding. Therefore, null hypothesis was rejected.

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between leadership consistency and strategic educational planning among academic staffs of Nigerian Colleges. The hypothesis was tested using Pearson product moment correlation and the result is presented on Table 3.

Table 3: Summary of Pearson product moment correlation showing the relationship between leadership consistency and strategic educational planning

	1	2	\bar{X}	SD
Strategic educational planning	1		1.50	.50
Leadership consistency	.435**	1	15.79	3.13

**** Significant at 0.01**

The result from table 3 indicated a statistically significant positive correlation between leadership consistency and strategic educational planning, with a correlation coefficient of $r = .435^{**}$ and a p-value < 0.01 . This suggested that as leadership consistency increased, strategic educational planning tended to improve in a meaningful way. The strength of the relationship, with a moderate effect size, indicated that leadership consistency played a substantial role in enhancing strategic educational planning within an educational context. The symbol asterisk (**) confirmed that this relationship was highly significant at the 1% level, reinforcing the reliability of this finding. Therefore, null hypothesis was rejected.

Discussion

The results that tested the first hypothesis revealed a statistically significant positive correlation between leadership behavioural integrity and strategic educational planning. This implied that as leadership behavioural integrity increased, strategic educational planning tended to improve meaningfully. The findings of this study aligned with those of Al-Mahdi (2021), who reported that both transformational and transactional leadership styles played diverse and vital roles in the strategic planning processes of colleges, contributing to their overall success. Similarly, Oga and Eketu (2022) found that leaders' integrity significantly and directly influenced workers' productive

behaviour.

The second hypothesis revealed a statistically significant positive correlation between leadership moral behaviour and strategic educational planning. This implied that as leadership moral behaviour increased, strategic educational planning increased in a meaningful way. The findings of this study aligned with previous research by Karnama and Tafreshi (2015), who reported that moral leadership has a significantly positive effect on organizational performance. Similarly, Broome and Marshall (2020) highlighted a significant relationship and impact between leadership styles and strategic planning. Additionally, Fadhil et al. (2021) found that moral intelligence played a crucial role in strengthening the positive relationship in strategic leadership.

The third hypothesis revealed a statistically significant positive correlation between leadership consistency and strategic educational planning. This implies that as leadership consistency increased, strategic educational planning increased in a meaningful way. The result of this study is consistent with previous findings by Okeleke and Agwoje (2023) who found a significant relationship between leaders' strategic planning method and effective management with focus on the key variables of strategic analysis, strategic formulation, and strategic implementation.

Conclusion

The study has contributed to knowledge by examining the dynamics of strategic educational planning in promoting leadership integrity in Nigerian colleges. The results revealed a statistically significant positive correlation between leadership behavioural integrity and strategic educational planning. Similarly, a statistically significant positive correlation was found between leadership moral behaviour and strategic educational planning. Additionally, leadership consistency also demonstrated a statistically significant positive correlation with strategic educational planning. In addition, these findings implied that as leadership behavioural integrity, leadership moral behaviour, and leadership consistency increase, strategic educational planning also increased in a meaningful and impactful manner.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to be implemented:

Managements in Nigerian Colleges of Education should prioritize leadership integrity by implementing policies that promote leadership behavioural integrity, leadership moral behaviour, and leadership consistency among administrators and educators.

Regular training and workshops should be organized for college leaders to reinforce ethical leadership, transparency, and consistency in decision-making to enhance strategic educational planning.

Colleges should establish and enforce clear guidelines that encourage integrity and ethical leadership in all educational planning and administrative activities.

Effective collaboration between educational stakeholders, including government agencies, institutional management, and faculty members, should be strengthened to support integrity-driven strategic planning.

Limitations of Study and Implications for Future Research

The study was limited to the academic staff of Nigerian colleges in the Southwest zone. Based on these limitations, researchers aiming to replicate this study should consider increasing the sample size and including academic staff from related institutions. The data collected were based on subjective reports from respondents, using validated scales. Future research could identify and investigate more objective factors of strategic educational planning in promoting leadership integrity to enhance data objectivity.

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